

A GEOMETRIC RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CONTINUED FRACTIONS AND CLEAN LATTICE PARALLELOGRAMS

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Abstract

The interior hull of a lattice polygon is the convex closure of the set of lattice points lying in the interior of the polygon. In this paper, we give a concrete description of the interior hull of a clean lattice parallelogram. A clean parallelogram in \mathbb{R}^2 is a lattice parallelogram whose boundary contains no lattice points other than its vertices. Using unimodular maps, we can identify a clean parallelogram with a parallelogram, $P_{a,n}$, whose vertices are $(0,0)$, $(1,0)$, (a,n) , and $(a+1,n)$, with $0 < a < n$ and $\gcd(a,n) = 1$. We employ Stark's geometric formulation of the continued fraction algorithm to show that the convergents of the continued fraction expansion of n/a (viewed as lattice points) appear in a one-to-two correspondence with the vertices of the interior hull of this parallelogram. Consequently, if the continued fraction expansion of n/a has many partial quotients, then the interior hull of the corresponding parallelogram has many vertices. A further consequence of this one-to-two correspondence is an elementary geometric interpretation of the sum of the partial quotients of the continued fraction expansion of n/a . Specifically, it is the difference between the area of the clean parallelogram $P_{a,n}$ and the area of its interior hull.

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1. Introduction

A lattice polygon in \mathbb{R}^2 is a polygon all of whose vertices belong to the integer lattice \mathbb{Z}^2 . The aim of this paper is to describe how continued fractions provide a concrete description of the interior hull of a clean lattice parallelogram. Here, the adjective “clean” means that the only lattice points on the boundary are the vertices. The concept of the interior hull is as follows.

Definition 1. Let $P \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ be a lattice polygon containing at least one lattice point in its interior. The interior hull of P , denoted by $P^{(1)}$, is the convex closure of the set of lattice points in the interior of P , that is,

$$P^{(1)} = \text{conv}(\text{interior}(P) \cap \mathbb{Z}^2).$$

In the case of a lattice rectangle (with a horizontal base), the interior hull is uninteresting. It is either a lattice rectangle, a point, or a set of lattice points arranged vertically or horizontally. Our initial goal was to find examples of lattice parallelograms P where $P^{(1)}$ has a large number of vertices and to understand the structure of this set. A natural place to start is by focusing on clean parallelograms. The reason for this is that by using unimodular maps we can identify a clean parallelogram with a parallelogram, $P_{a,n}$, of the form

$$P_{a,n} = \{s(1, 0) + t(a, n) : 1 \leq a < n, \text{gcd}(a, n) = 1, 0 \leq s, t \leq 1\}.$$

At this juncture, the reader may want to skip ahead to Figure 4 in Section 5 to see a detailed picture of $P_{11,29}$ and $P_{11,29}^{(1)}$.

1.1. Main Result

Our main result is Theorem 6. Here we prove that the convergents of the continued fraction expansion of n/a (viewed as lattice points) appear in a one-to-two correspondence with the vertices of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$. Consequently, if the continued fraction expansion of n/a has many partial quotients, then $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$ has many vertices. Another interesting consequence is Equation (3) which gives an elementary geometric interpretation of the sum of the partial quotients of the continued fraction expansion of n/a .

1.2. An Aside

The inception of our work stems from the paper [3] in which we first learned of the concept of the interior hull. We give a short summary of the paper.

Scott [10] proved a beautiful inequality for convex lattice polygons that contain at least one interior lattice point. The inequality states that

$$n_{bd} \leq 2n_{int} + 7,$$

where n_{int} and n_{bd} are, respectively, the number of lattice points in the interior and on the boundary of the polygon. Hasse and Schicho [3] improved on Scott’s inequality by introducing a discrete analogue of the radius of the incircle in Euclidean geometry. They called this new invariant the *level* and denoted it as l . They then proved the stronger inequality

$$(2l - 1)n_{bd} \leq 2n_{int} + 9l^2 - 2$$

for $l \geq 1$. The notion of the level is as follows. We can obtain a nested sequence of interior hulls

$$P^{(1)} \supseteq P^{(2)} \supseteq P^{(3)} \supseteq \dots,$$

where $P^{(2)}$ is the interior hull of $P^{(1)}$, $P^{(3)}$ is the interior hull of $P^{(2)}$, and so on, until we find a n such that $P^{(n+1)} = \emptyset$. The integer n is essentially the level modulo some technicalities. Hasse and Schicho proved their inequality by considering the nested sequence of interior hulls and then peeling off these hulls. Since this peeling process is reminiscent of peeling the layers of an onion, they gave their inequality the picturesque name “The Onion-Skin Theorem”!

In this paper, we have restricted ourselves to studying only the first interior hull, $P^{(1)}$. A future project is to investigate the interior hulls $P^{(2)}, P^{(3)}, \dots$ for clean lattice parallelograms.

2. Some Preliminaries

A natural tool in our work is the concept of a unimodular map — the maps that preserve the lattice \mathbb{Z}^n .

Definition 2. An *affine unimodular map* is an affine map

$$\mathcal{T} : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n \text{ of the form } \mathcal{T}(\mathbf{x}) = M\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{u},$$

where $M \in GL_n(\mathbb{Z})$, $\det(M) = \pm 1$, and $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{Z}^n$.

We typically omit the word “affine” when discussing such maps. Such maps give a natural definition of equivalence for lattice polygons.

Definition 3. Two lattice polygons P_1 and P_2 are said to be *unimodularly equivalent* if there is a unimodular map \mathcal{T} such that $\mathcal{T}(P_1) = \mathcal{T}(P_2)$.

Let P be a lattice parallelogram. Since translation by a lattice point preserves the lattice structure, we may assume, without loss of generality, that one of the vertices of P is the origin and that P is of the form

$$P = \{s\mathbf{u} + t\mathbf{v} : \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{Z}^2, 0 \leq s, t \leq 1\}.$$

In the study of such parallelograms it is sometimes convenient to examine the quotient group $(\mathbb{Z} \oplus \mathbb{Z})/(\mathbb{Z}\mathbf{u} \oplus \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{v})$. A basic result for this group of quotients is as follows.

Theorem 1. *Let $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, u_2), \mathbf{v} = (v_1, v_2) \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ be linearly independent. Then,*

$$\# \left(\frac{\mathbb{Z} \oplus \mathbb{Z}}{\mathbb{Z}\mathbf{u} \oplus \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{v}} \right) = |u_1v_2 - u_2v_1|.$$

That is, the cardinality of the quotient group equals the area of the parallelogram spanned by \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} .

Two results that we will use are as follows. The first being the famous theorem of Pick [1] on lattice polygons.

Theorem 2 (Pick, 1899). *The area of any (not necessarily convex) lattice polygon $Q \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ is given by*

$$\text{area}(Q) = n_{int} + \frac{1}{2}n_{bd} - 1,$$

where n_{int} and n_{bd} are, respectively, the number of lattice points in the interior and on the boundary of Q .

Lemma 1. *Let P be a lattice parallelogram spanned by the lattice points $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, u_2)$ and $\mathbf{v} = (v_1, v_2)$. Let T_1 be the lattice triangle with vertices $\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{u}$, and \mathbf{v} , and let T_2 be the lattice triangle with vertices \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} , and $\mathbf{u} + \mathbf{v}$, that is, T_1, T_2 are the two triangles formed by the antidiagonal of P . Then the correspondence*

$$s\mathbf{u} + t\mathbf{v} \leftrightarrow (1 - s)\mathbf{u} + (1 - t)\mathbf{v}, \text{ with } 0 < s, t < 1,$$

gives a bijective correspondence between the points of T_1 and the points of T_2 that lie in the interior of P .

3. Clean Parallelograms and a Reduction Result

For the remainder of the paper we will work with clean parallelograms. The word “clean” was introduced by Reznick in [9].

Definition 4. A lattice parallelogram in \mathbb{R}^2 is said to be *clean* if the only lattice points on its sides are the vertices. If a clean lattice parallelogram does not contain any lattice points in its interior, then we call it an *empty* parallelogram.

We remind the reader that $P_{a,n}$ denotes the clean parallelogram with vertices $(0, 0), (1, 0), (a, n)$, and $(a + 1, n)$, with $1 \leq a < n$ and $\text{gcd}(a, n) = 1$. Since unimodular maps preserve \mathbb{Z}^2 , they map clean parallelograms to clean parallelograms. In our next result we apply this property to show that a clean parallelogram is (unimodularly) equivalent to some $P_{a,n}$. To illustrate our proof we examine a specific example.

Example 1. The clean parallelogram

$$P = \{s(16, 9) + t(4, 7) : 0 \leq s, t \leq 1\}$$

is unimodularly equivalent to $P_{43,76}$.

Proof. Since

$$\det \left(\begin{pmatrix} 16 & 4 \\ 9 & 7 \end{pmatrix} \right) = 76,$$

we get that $n = 76$. The next step is to use the extended Euclidean algorithm to express 1 as an integer linear combination of 16 and 9. We have

$$4 \cdot 16 + (-7) \cdot 9 = 1,$$

and we write the unimodular matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 4 & -7 \\ -9 & 16 \end{pmatrix}.$$

This gives us

$$\begin{pmatrix} 4 & -7 \\ -9 & 16 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 16 & 4 \\ 9 & 7 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -33 \\ 0 & 76 \end{pmatrix}.$$

We conclude that $a = 43$ via the calculation

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -33 \\ 0 & 76 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 43 \\ 0 & 76 \end{pmatrix}.$$

□

Theorem 3. *Let P be the clean lattice parallelogram spanned by the lattice points \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} with $\text{area}(P) = n$. Then there is a unimodular map $T : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ such that*

$$T(P) = P_{a,n}, \text{ with } 1 \leq a < n \text{ and } \gcd(a, n) = 1.$$

Proof. We begin by observing that there are precisely $(n - 1)$ lattice points in the interior of P . This follows by combining Pick's theorem with the hypotheses that $\text{area}(P) = n$ and that the only lattice points on the boundary of P are the vertices. (Another way to obtain this is to observe that each lattice point in the interior of P denotes a distinct non-zero coset of $(\mathbb{Z} \oplus \mathbb{Z})/(\mathbb{Z}\mathbf{u} \oplus \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{v})$ and each vertex of P represents the zero coset.)

Without loss of generality, we may assume that the pair of lattice points $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, u_2), \mathbf{v} = (v_1, v_2)$ is positively oriented, that is, $\det(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) > 0$. Since $\gcd(u_1, u_2) = 1$, there exist $m_1, m_2 \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that

$$m_1 u_1 + m_2 u_2 = 1.$$

We now consider the unimodular matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} m_1 & m_2 \\ -u_2 & u_1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

This unimodular matrix maps P to the clean parallelogram

$$P' = \{t_1(1, 0) + t_2(m_1v_1 + m_2v_2, n) : 0 \leq t_1, t_2 \leq 1\}.$$

If $0 < (m_1v_1 + m_2v_2) < n$, then $a = m_1v_1 + m_2v_2$. If $(m_1v_1 + m_2v_2)$ does not satisfy the above inequality, then we find $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $0 \leq (m_1v_1 + m_2v_2 + kn) < n$ and act on P' by the unimodular matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & k \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

to obtain $P_{a,n}$. □

Lemma 2. *Let $a, n \in \mathbb{N}$ with $n > 1$ and $\gcd(a, n) = 1$. Furthermore, let a^{-1} denote the unique integer in the interval $[1, n - 1]$ such that $aa^{-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{n}$. Then the clean parallelograms*

$$P_{a,n}, P_{n-a,n}, P_{a^{-1},n}, P_{n-a^{-1},n}$$

are unimodularly equivalent.

Proof. The unimodular map

$$\mathbf{x} \mapsto \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{x} + \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

shows that $P_{n-a,n}$ is unimodularly equivalent to $P_{a,n}$.

By the extended Euclidean algorithm there exist $m \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $a^{-1}a + mn = 1$. The unimodular map

$$\mathbf{x} \mapsto \begin{pmatrix} a^{-1} & m \\ n & -a \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{x}$$

shows that $P_{a^{-1},n}$ is unimodularly equivalent to $P_{a,n}$. □

A nice aspect of working with $P_{a,n}$ is that we can easily generate the lattice points in its interior by observing that the lattice point $(1, 1)$ is a generator of the cyclic group $(\mathbb{Z} \oplus \mathbb{Z}) / (\mathbb{Z}(1, 0) \oplus \mathbb{Z}(a, n))$. Specifically, we have the following result.

Lemma 3. *The lattice points in the interior of $P_{a,n}$ are of the form*

$$\left\langle \frac{k(n-a)}{n} \right\rangle (1, 0) + \frac{k}{n}(a, n), \quad k = 1, \dots, n-1.$$

An elaboration of Lemma 1 gives an instructive aspect of the parallelograms $P_{a,n}$.

Lemma 4. *The unimodular map $\mathcal{S} : P_{a,n} \rightarrow P_{a,n}$ via*

$$\mathcal{S}((x, y)) = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} a+1 \\ n \end{pmatrix}.$$

is an isometry.

At this juncture we make some simple observations about the vertices of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$. Let l_k denote the vertical line $x = k$. For $k = 1, \dots, a$ let

$$S_k = l_k \cap \text{interior}(P_{a,n}) \cap \mathbb{Z}^2.$$

We note that

$$\text{interior}(P_{a,n}) \cap \mathbb{Z}^2 = \cup_1^a S_k.$$

Let $L(S_k)$ and $H(S_k)$ be, respectively, the lowest and highest point in S_k . Noting that any point lying between $L(S_k)$ and $H(S_k)$ cannot be a vertex of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$, we conclude that

$$P_{a,n}^{(1)} = \text{conv}(\{L(S_k), H(S_k) : k = 1, \dots, a\}).$$

Lemma 5. *If $a = 1$, then $L(S_1) = (1, 1)$ and $H(S_1) = (1, n - 1)$. If $a > 1$, then*

$$L(S_1) = (1, 1), H(S_1) = \left(1, \left\lfloor \frac{n}{a} \right\rfloor\right);$$

$$L(S_k) = \left(k, \left\lceil \frac{(k-1)n}{a} \right\rceil\right), H(S_k) = \left(k, \left\lfloor \frac{kn}{a} \right\rfloor\right) \text{ for } k = 2, \dots, a-1;$$

and

$$L(S_a) = \left(a, \left\lceil \frac{(a-1)n}{a} \right\rceil\right), H(S_a) = (a, n-1).$$

Lemma 6. *Let $k, l \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, with $k + l = a + 1$. Then*

$$L(S_k) + H(S_l) = (a + 1, n),$$

that is,

$$H(S_l) = \mathcal{S}(L(S_k)) \text{ and } L(S_k) = \mathcal{S}(H(S_l)).$$

It follows that $H(S_l)$ is a point on the boundary of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$ if and only if $L(S_k)$ is a point on the boundary of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$.

4. Stark’s Geometric Formulation of the Continued Fraction Algorithm

In this aside we give a synopsis of Stark’s approach to continued fractions [11, Chapter 7]. It is an elaboration of Klein’s geometric interpretation of the continued fraction expansion of an irrational number (see [2, Chapter 4, Section 12]). A

streamlined version of Stark’s geometric approach is given in Irwin’s expository paper [4].

Klein’s visualization of continued fractions is as follows. Let α be a positive number. Typically α is irrational and consequently has an infinite continued fraction expansion. However, what we are describing also applies when α is rational with the only difference being that the continued fraction expansion is then finite.

Consider the line $y = \alpha x$, and let A/B be a convergent arising from the continued fraction expansion of α . Then (B, A) is the lattice point closest to the line $y = \alpha x$ among all the lattice points in the first quadrant that have x -coordinate less than or equal to B ; that is, if a lattice point (B', A') , with $A', B' > 0$, is closer to $y = \alpha x$ than (B, A) , then $B' > B$. Let

$$\frac{A_0}{B_0}, \frac{A_1}{B_1}, \dots, \frac{A_k}{B_k}, \dots$$

denote the convergents of α . A basic inequality in continued fractions is

$$\frac{A_0}{B_0} < \frac{A_2}{B_2} < \frac{A_4}{B_4} < \dots < \alpha < \dots < \frac{A_5}{B_5} < \frac{A_3}{B_3} < \frac{A_1}{B_1}.$$

Consequently we can view the lattice points with even subscripts,

$$(B_0, A_0), (B_2, A_2), (B_4, A_4), \dots,$$

as lying to the right of the line $y = \alpha x$ (or lying below the line), and the lattice points with odd subscripts,

$$(B_1, A_1), (B_3, A_3), (B_5, A_5), \dots,$$

as lying to the left of the line $y = \alpha x$ (or lying above the line). This visual of left and right (or above or below) will play an important role in the proof of our main result. With this geometric viewpoint, Stark rephrased the continued fraction algorithm in the following manner.

- Algorithm 1** (CF algorithm). 1. Set $\mathbf{v}_{-2} = (1, 0)$ and $\mathbf{v}_{-1} = (0, 1)$.
2. Set $\mathbf{v}_0 = \mathbf{v}_{-2} + q_0\mathbf{v}_{-1}$, where q_0 is the largest non-negative integer such that $\mathbf{v}_{-2} + q_0\mathbf{v}_{-1}$ lies below the line $y = \alpha x$, but $\mathbf{v}_{-2} + (q_0 + 1)\mathbf{v}_{-1}$ lies above the line $y = \alpha x$.
3. In general, $\mathbf{v}_i = \mathbf{v}_{i-2} + q_i\mathbf{v}_{i-1}$, where q_i is the largest integer such that $\mathbf{v}_{i-2} + q_i\mathbf{v}_{i-1}$ lies on the same side of the line $y = \alpha x$ as \mathbf{v}_{i-2} , but $\mathbf{v}_{i-2} + (q_i + 1)\mathbf{v}_{i-1}$ lies on the opposite side of $y = \alpha x$.
4. The algorithm terminates if \mathbf{v}_i lies on the line $y = \alpha x$.

Figure 1: The CF algorithm

For the rest of this section we will use the notation introduced in the above algorithm. A basic theorem on continued fractions can be rephrased as follows (see [11, Theorem 7.20]).

Theorem 4. For $i = -2, -1, 0, 1, \dots$,

$$\det(\mathbf{v}_i, \mathbf{v}_{i+1}) = (-1)^i. \tag{1}$$

Consequently, the parallelogram spanned by \mathbf{v}_i and \mathbf{v}_{i+1} does not contain any non-vertex lattice points, and $\mathbb{Z}\mathbf{v}_i \oplus \mathbb{Z}\mathbf{v}_{i+1} = \mathbb{Z}^2$.

Let $a, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ with $a < n$ and $\gcd(a, n) = 1$. Let $\mathbf{v}_{-2} = (1, 0)$, and $\mathbf{v}_{-1} = (0, 1)$. We express the continued fraction expansion expansion of n/a as

$$\begin{aligned} (B_0, A_0) = \mathbf{v}_0 &= \mathbf{v}_{-2} + q_0 \mathbf{v}_{-1} \\ (B_1, A_1) = \mathbf{v}_1 &= \mathbf{v}_{-1} + q_1 \mathbf{v}_0 \\ (B_2, A_2) = \mathbf{v}_2 &= \mathbf{v}_0 + q_2 \mathbf{v}_1 \\ &\vdots \\ (B_{m-1}, A_{m-1}) = \mathbf{v}_{m-1} &= \mathbf{v}_{m-3} + q_{m-1} \mathbf{v}_{m-2} \\ (a, n) = \mathbf{v}_m &= \mathbf{v}_{m-2} + q_m \mathbf{v}_{m-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1 is a visual illustration of the continued fraction algorithm. We warn the reader that we have taken some artistic liberties. Specifically, we have chosen the vector \mathbf{v}_{i-1} to be horizontal and the vector \mathbf{v}_{i-2} to be vertical; in reality they both have positive slope. Furthermore, we have only indicated some of the lattice points that lie on the boundary of the parallelogram with vertices $(0, 0), \mathbf{v}_{i-2}, \mathbf{v}_i$, and $q_i \mathbf{v}_{i-1}$. There are no lattice points on the line segment connecting $(0, 0)$ to \mathbf{v}_{i-2} other than the endpoints. The same remark holds for the line segment connecting $q_i \mathbf{v}_{i-1}$ to \mathbf{v}_i . However, on the line segment connecting $(0, 0)$ to $q_i \mathbf{v}_{i-1}$ there are $q_i - 1$ lattice points in addition to the end points. The same remark holds for the line segment connecting \mathbf{v}_{i-2} to \mathbf{v}_i .

The following little lemma shows that $q_m \geq 2$, and consequently there is at least one lattice point lying on the open line segment connecting \mathbf{v}_{m-2} and \mathbf{v}_m . We will need this observation when we are determining the vertices of $P_{a,n}$.

Lemma 7. *We recall that $[q_0, q_1, q_2, \dots, q_m]$ is the continued fraction expansion of n/a . We have the inequality*

$$q_m \geq 2.$$

Proof. We apply the Euclidean algorithm with n and a . The steps are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} n &= q_0 a + r_0 \\ a &= q_1 r_0 + r_1 \\ &\vdots \\ r_{m-4} &= q_{m-2} r_{m-3} + r_{m-2} \\ r_{m-3} &= q_{m-1} r_{m-2} + r_{m-1} \\ r_{m-2} &= q_m r_{m-1}, \end{aligned}$$

with $r_0 > r_1 > \dots > r_{m-2} > r_{m-1} = 1$. Since $r_{m-1} = 1$, we conclude

$$q_m = r_{m-2} > 1.$$

□

5. Continued Fractions and the Boundary of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$

In the preceding sections, we have discussed the context of our problem and laid the groundwork to tackle it. We now focus on proving our main result; that is, we use the continued fraction expansion of n/a to give a concrete description of the vertices of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$. Afterwards, we discuss various numeric and geometric consequences.

5.1. A Menagerie of Notations and Preliminary Results

In this section we discuss some results about the convergents of a continued fraction. Some of them will be used in the proof of our main theorem; others are there to illuminate the geometry.

Theorem 5. *For $i = 0, 1, \dots, m-1$, let d_i be the distance from (B_i, A_i) to the line $y = (n/a)x$. We then have the strictly decreasing sequence*

$$\frac{\text{width}(P_{a,n})}{2} = \frac{n}{2\sqrt{n^2 + a^2}} > d_0 > d_1 > d_2 > \dots > d_{m-1} > 0.$$

Figure 2: Subdividing $P_{a,n}$

Furthermore, let (β, α) be a lattice point in the interior of the rectangle with vertices $(0, 0), (0, n), (a, 0),$ and (a, n) satisfying the following conditions:

$$0 < \beta \leq B_i, (\beta, \alpha) \neq (B_{i-1}, A_{i-1}), (\beta, \alpha) \neq (B_i, A_i).$$

Then, $d > d_{i-1}$, where d is the distance of (β, α) to the line $y = (n/a)x$.

For a proof of Theorem 5 see [11, Theorem 7.15]. We now use the lines $y = (n/a)(x - 0.5)$ and $y = n/2$ to subdivide $P_{a,n}$ into four smaller parallelograms $P_1, P_2, P_3,$ and P_4 (see Figure 2). These four parallelograms provide a helpful visual partition of the vertices of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$.

Lemma 8. Let V_1 and V_2 denote the sets

$$V_1 = \{(B_0, A_0), (B_2, A_2), (B_4, A_4), \dots, (B_{E(m)}, A_{E(m)})\},$$

$$V_2 = \{(B_1 + 1, A_1), (B_3 + 1, A_3), (B_5 + 1, A_5), \dots, (B_{O(m)} + 1, A_{O(m)})\},$$

where $E(m)$ denotes the largest even integer less than m , and $O(m)$ denotes the largest odd integer less than m . Then, $V_1 \subset P_1, \mathcal{S}(V_1) \subset P_3, V_2 \subset P_2,$ and $\mathcal{S}(V_2) \subset P_4$, where \mathcal{S} is the unimodular map $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{v}) = -\mathbf{v} + (a + 1, n)$.

Proof. We begin by showing that the points in V_1 and V_2 lie below the horizontal line $y = n/2$ and the points in $\mathcal{S}(V_1)$ and $\mathcal{S}(V_2)$ lie above the horizontal line $y = n/2$. We observe the following:

1. The points in V_1 lie to the right of the line $y = (n/a)x$ and the points in V_2 lie to the left of the line $y = (n/a)(x - 1)$.
2. We have the following sequence of inequalities:

$$1 \leq A_0 < A_1 < \dots < A_{m-1} < A_m = n.$$

In Lemma 7 we derived the inequality $q_m \geq 2$. Using this inequality we get

$$n = A_{m-2} + q_m A_{m-1} > q_m A_{m-1} \geq 2A_{m-1}$$

and conclude that

$$n/2 > A_i$$

for $i = 0, \dots, m - 1$. Furthermore, the y -coordinates of the points in $\mathcal{S}(V_1) \cup \mathcal{S}(V_2)$ are of the form $n - A_i$. Consequently the points in V_1 and V_2 lie below the horizontal line $y = n/2$ and the points in $\mathcal{S}(V_1)$ and $\mathcal{S}(V_2)$ lie above the line $y = n/2$.

We now show that the convergent $(1, A_0)$ lies in the interior of P_1 . The point $(1, A_0)$ lies below the line $y = (n/a)x$ and does not lie on the line $y = (n/a)(x - 1/2)$. If $(1, A_0)$ lay below the line $y = (n/a)(x - 1/2)$, then the lattice point $(1, 2A_0)$ would lie below the line $y = (n/a)x$ and would be closer to $y = (n/a)x$ than $(1, A_0)$. This contradicts Theorem 5. Consequently, $(1, A_0)$ must lie inside P_1 .

We now recall that the distances of the points in V_1 to the line $y = (n/a)x$ are $d_0, d_2, \dots, d_{E(m)}$ and the distances of the points in V_2 to the line $y = (n/a)(x - 1)$ are $d_1, d_3, \dots, d_{O(m)}$. Since

$$\text{width}(P_1) = \text{width}(P_2) > d_0 > d_1 > \dots > d_{m-1},$$

we conclude that $V_1 \subset P_1$ and $V_2 \subset P_2$. Finally, a routine check shows that $\mathcal{S}(P_1) = P_3$ and $\mathcal{S}(P_2) = P_4$. □

The next lemma follows immediately from examining Figure 1 and applying Theorem 4. However, we apply Pick's theorem to give a proof.

Lemma 9. *For $i = 0, 1, \dots, m$, consider the triangle, T_i , with vertices $(0, 0)$, \mathbf{v}_{i-2} , and \mathbf{v}_i . Then we have the following:*

1. *There are $q_i + 1$ lattice points on the line segment connecting \mathbf{v}_{i-2} to \mathbf{v}_i .*
2. *There are no lattice points in the interior of T_i .*
3. *All of the non-vertex lattice points in T_i lie on the line segment connecting \mathbf{v}_{i-2} to \mathbf{v}_i .*

Proof. The reader may want to refer to Figure 1. We have that

$$\mathbf{v}_i - \mathbf{v}_{i-2} = \mathbf{v}_{i-2} + q_i \mathbf{v}_{i-1} - \mathbf{v}_{i-2} = q_i(B_{i-1}, A_{i-1}).$$

It follows that the number of lattice points on the line segment connecting \mathbf{v}_{i-2} to \mathbf{v}_i equals

$$q_i \gcd(B_{i-1}, A_{i-1}) + 1 = q_i + 1.$$

Furthermore, since \mathbf{v}_{i-2} and \mathbf{v}_i are convergents, there are no non-vertex lattice points on the other two sides of T_i . Combining these two remarks we conclude that there are $q_i + 2$ lattice points on the boundary of T_i .

The following calculation gives the area of T_i :

$$\text{area}(T_i) = |\det(\mathbf{v}_{i-2}, \mathbf{v}_i)|/2 = |q_i \det(\mathbf{v}_{i-2}, \mathbf{v}_{i-1})|/2 = q_i/2,$$

where the last step follows from Theorem 4. We now invoke Pick’s theorem to conclude that T_i does not contain any interior lattice points, and consequently all of the non-vertex lattice points in T_i lie on the edge connecting \mathbf{v}_{i-2} to \mathbf{v}_i . \square

From here onward, we use $\gamma(\mathbf{w}_1, \mathbf{w}_2, \dots, \mathbf{w}_n)$ to denote the piecewise linear path that connects \mathbf{w}_1 to \mathbf{w}_2 , \mathbf{w}_2 to \mathbf{w}_3 , and so on.

Lemma 10. For $i = 0, \dots, m - 2$,

$$\det \begin{pmatrix} 1 & B_{i-2} & A_{i-2} \\ 1 & B_i & A_i \\ 1 & B_{i+2} & A_{i+2} \end{pmatrix} = (-1)^{i-1} q_i q_{i+1} q_{i+2}.$$

Consequently, when traversing the piecewise linear paths

$$\gamma(\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_3, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{O(m)}) \text{ and } \gamma(\mathbf{v}_{E(m)}, \mathbf{v}_{E(m)-2}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_0),$$

we are always turning to the left.

5.2. Our Main Theorem

We introduce the following notation. For $i = -2, -1, \dots, m$ let

$$\mathbf{u}_i = \mathbf{v}_i + (1, 0).$$

We note that $\mathbf{u}_{-1} = (1, 1)$ and $\mathbf{u}_m = (a + 1, n)$. Lemmas 9 and 10 are our tools for proving Theorem 6.

Theorem 6. Let $a, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ with $a < n$ and $\gcd(a, n) = 1$. Let $[q_0, q_1, \dots, q_m]$ be the continued fraction expansion of n/a with $m \geq 2$. Then the boundary of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$ is given by the paths

$$\gamma(\mathbf{u}_{-1}, \mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_3, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{O(m)}, \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{v}_{E(m)}),$$

Figure 3: A schematic diagram of $P_{a,n}$ with $R_0 = P_{a,n}^{(1)}$

$$\begin{aligned} &\gamma(\mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{v}_{E(m)}, \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{v}_{E(m)-2}, \dots, \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{v}_0, \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{u}_{-1}), \\ &\gamma(\mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{u}_3, \dots, \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{u}_{O(m)}, \mathbf{v}_{E(m)}), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\gamma(\mathbf{v}_{E(m)}, \mathbf{v}_{E(m)-2}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_0, \mathbf{u}_{-1}).$$

Furthermore, these lattice points are the vertices of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$.

There are two points are worth noting. The lattice point $\mathbf{u}_{-1} = (1, 1)$ is always a vertex of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$. Furthermore, when $2a > n$, then $\mathbf{v}_0 = (1, 1)$ and $\mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{v}_0 = \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{u}_{-1}$.

Proof. We begin by observing that there are two possible cases:

$$(i) E(m) < O(m); \quad (ii) O(m) < E(m).$$

Since the proofs for the two cases are identical, we restrict ourselves to the first case, that is, $E(m) < O(m)$. The essence of the proof is captured in Figure 3. Before proceeding with our proof we make some clarifying remarks about this picture.

In the picture we assume that $2a < n$ (that is, $\mathbf{v}_0 \neq (1, 1)$) and $E(m) < O(m)$, and we retain this assumption in our proof. (The distinction between the cases $\mathbf{v}_0 \neq (1, 1)$ and $\mathbf{v}_0 = (1, 1)$ is trivial.) We list some aspects of Figure 3. (At this juncture the reader may want to compare Figure 3 with Figure 4.)

1. A dashed line represents a piecewise linear path. The dotted lines show us the decomposition of $P_{a,n}$ into the 4 congruent parallelograms P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4 .
2. The pt_i 's are the following lattice points: $pt_1 = \mathbf{u}_{-1}$, $pt_2 = \mathbf{u}_{O(m)}$, $pt_3 = \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{v}_{E(m)}$, $pt_4 = \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{v}_0$, $pt_5 = \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{u}_{-1}$, $pt_6 = \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{u}_{O(m)}$, $pt_7 = \mathbf{v}_{E(m)}$, $pt_8 = \mathbf{v}_0$.
3. The point pt_6 is the *highest* lattice point on the line segment connecting $\mathbf{v}_{E(m)}$ to (a, n) that is distinct from (a, n) . Since

$$(a, n) = \mathbf{v}_{E(m)} + q_m \mathbf{v}_{O(m)},$$

we conclude that

$$pt_6 = \mathbf{v}_{E(m)} + (q_m - 1)\mathbf{v}_{O(m)} = \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{u}_{O(m)}.$$

4. In Figure 3 the paths γ_1, γ_2 are

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma(\mathbf{u}_{-1}, \mathbf{u}_1, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{O(m)}) \text{ and } \gamma_2 = \gamma(\mathbf{v}_0, \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{E(m)}).$$

5. Let Γ be the closed path:

$$\Gamma = \gamma_1 \cup \gamma(pt_2, pt_3) \cup \mathcal{S}(\gamma_2) \cup \gamma(pt_4, pt_5) \cup \mathcal{S}(\gamma_1) \cup \gamma(pt_6, pt_7) \cup \gamma_2 \cup \gamma(pt_8, pt_1).$$

The polygonal region enclosed by Γ is denoted R_0 . Our labelling of the points pt_1, \dots, pt_8 in Figure 3 illustrates our visualization of Γ as starting at pt_1 , then travelling counterclockwise and eventually returning to pt_1 .

6. We recall the notation from Lemma 9, where T_i denotes the triangle with vertices $(0, 0)$, \mathbf{v}_{i-2} and \mathbf{v}_i . We express the regions R_1, R_2 as

$$R_1 = \cup_{i=2, i \text{ even}}^{E(m)} T_i \text{ and } R_2 = \left(\cup_{i=1, i \text{ odd}}^{O(m)} T_i \right) + (1, 0).$$

Our goal is to prove that

$$R_0 = P_{a,n}^{(1)}.$$

We do so by demonstrating the inclusion

$$\text{interior}(P_{a,n}) \cap \mathbb{Z}^2 \subset R_0$$

and that R_0 is a convex polygon.

In Lemma 9 we proved that the triangles T_i did not contain any interior lattice points. Consequently, there are no interior lattice points in any of the regions T_m, R_1, T_0 and R_2 . Furthermore, since $\mathcal{S}(\mathbf{v}) = -\mathbf{v} + (a + 1, n)$ is a unimodular map, the same remark holds for the regions $\mathcal{S}(T_m), \mathcal{S}(R_1), \mathcal{S}(T_0)$, and $\mathcal{S}(R_2)$. We now observe that the only lattice points on the line segments connecting (a, m) to $pt_6 = \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{u}_{O(m)}$, $(0, 0)$ to $pt_7 = \mathbf{v}_{E(m)}$, $(0, 0)$ to $pt_8 = \mathbf{v}_0$, and $\mathbf{u}_{-1} = (1, 1)$ to $(1, 0)$ are just the endpoints. This permits us to conclude that the elements of the set $((P_{a,n} - R_0) \cap \mathbb{Z}^2)$ are simply the 4 vertices of $P_{a,n}$.

Lemma 10 tells us that when we traverse the boundary of R_0 , starting at pt_1 and travelling counterclockwise, we are always turning left at the corners. Therefore, R_0 is convex and we conclude that $R_0 = P_{a,n}^{(1)}$. \square

Remark 1. The hypothesis $m \geq 2$ in Theorem 6 ensures that $E(m) \geq 0$ and $O(m) \geq 1$. What if $m \leq 1$? In this remark, we address this possibility.

1. If $m = 0$, then $a = 1$. All of the lattice points in the interior of $P_{1,n}$ lie on the antidiagonal. Consequently, $\text{area}(P_{1,n}^{(1)}) = 0$.
2. We have that $m = 1$ if and only if $a|(n - 1)$. This separates into two cases.
 - (a) If $a = n - 1$, then all of the lattice points in the interior of $P_{n-1,n}$ lie on the diagonal. Consequently, $\text{area}(P_{n-1,n}^{(1)}) = 0$.
 - (b) If $a < n - 1$, then $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$ is a parallelogram. Specifically, it is the parallelogram with vertices $((1, 1), (1, (n - 1)/a), (a, \lceil (a - 1)n/a \rceil), \text{ and } (a, n - 1))$. (Since $a|(n - 1)$, $\lceil (a - 1)n/a \rceil$ simplifies to $n - (n - 1)/a$.) Furthermore, $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$ is unimodularly equivalent to the rectangle with vertices $(0, 0), (0, (n - 1 - a)/a), (a - 1, 0), \text{ and } (a - 1, (n - 1 - a)/a)$.

5.3. Some Numeric and Geometric Consequences of Theorem 6

We present some consequences of our work and a detailed figure of $P_{11,29}^{(1)}$ and $P_{11,29}$.²

Lemma 11. *Let $[q_0, q_1, \dots, q_m]$ denote the continued fraction expansion of n/a . Furthermore, we assume that $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$ has positive area. Then,*

$$\# \text{ vertices}(P_{a,n}^{(1)}) = \begin{cases} 2(m + 1), & q_0 > 1, \\ 2m, & q_0 = 1, \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

and

$$\sum_{i=0}^m q_i = \text{area}(P_{a,n}) - \text{area}(P_{a,n}^{(1)}). \tag{3}$$

Proof. We begin by addressing the case where $m = 1$. For this case, we have listed the vertices of $P_{a,n}$ in Remark 1. The information provided allows us to check that the Equations (2) and (3) hold when $m = 1$. For the remainder of the proof, we assume that $m \geq 2$. Counting the different lattice points listed in the statement of Theorem 6, we obtain Equation (2). The only detail that requires a modicum of care is determining the number of lattice points lying on the boundary of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$. We consider the case $q_0 > 1$, and carefully examine Figure 3. We repeatedly invoke Lemma 9 which tells us that the number of lattice points on the line segment connecting \mathbf{v}_{i-2} to \mathbf{v}_i is equal to $q_i + 1$.

Since $\gamma(pt_3, pt_2) = \mathcal{S}(\gamma(pt_7, pt_6))$ and $\gamma(pt_8, pt_1) = \mathcal{S}(\gamma(pt_4, pt_5))$, we have that

$$\#(\gamma(pt_7, pt_6) \cap \mathbb{Z}^2) = \#(\gamma(pt_3, pt_2) \cap \mathbb{Z}^2) = q_m,$$

$$\#(\gamma(pt_8, pt_1) \cap \mathbb{Z}^2) = \#(\gamma(pt_4, pt_5) \cap \mathbb{Z}^2) = q_0.$$

For the piecewise linear paths $\gamma_1, \mathcal{S}(\gamma_1), \gamma_2$, and $\mathcal{S}(\gamma_2)$, we have

$$\#(\gamma_2 \cap \mathbb{Z}^2) = \#(\mathcal{S}(\gamma_2) \cap \mathbb{Z}^2) = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=2, i \text{ even}}^{E(m)} q_i + 1, & m > 2, \\ 1, & m \leq 2, \end{cases}$$

and

$$\#(\gamma_1 \cap \mathbb{Z}^2) = \#(\mathcal{S}(\gamma_1) \cap \mathbb{Z}^2) = \sum_{i=1, i \text{ odd}}^{O(m)} q_i + 1.$$

On combining this numeric data, we conclude that

$$\#(\Gamma \cap \mathbb{Z}^2) = \sum_{i=0}^m 2q_i - 4.$$

²The Python code for Figure 4 can be found at:
<https://github.com/riazki/ConvexHullPar/blob/main/ConvexHullPar.ipynb> .

Figure 4: $P_{11,29}$ and $P_{11,29}^{(1)}$

We now use Pick’s theorem to conclude that

$$\text{area} \left(P_{a,n}^{(1)} \right) = n - \sum_{i=0}^m q_i. \tag{4}$$

Hence,

$$\sum_{i=0}^m q_i = \text{area}(P_{a,n}) - \text{area} \left(P_{a,n}^{(1)} \right).$$

The proof for the case $q_0 = 1$ is identical. □

Remark 2. We needed the hypothesis $\text{area} \left(P_{a,n}^{(1)} \right) > 0$ in Lemma 11 to enable us to apply Pick’s theorem. However, Equation (4) extends to the case when $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$ is degenerate, that is, consisting of a line segment. This occurs only when $a = 1$ or $a = n - 1$. In either of these two cases, the sum of the partial quotients is n .

Upon contemplating the proof of Lemma 11 we obtain a little curio involving the Fibonacci numbers.

Corollary 1. *Let F_k denote the k -th Fibonacci number. The lattice polygon $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$ is clean if and only if $(a, n) = (F_{m-1}, F_m)$ or $(a, n) = (F_{m-2}, F_m)$.*

Proof. The lattice polygon $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$ is clean if and only if the continued fraction expansion of n/a is $[1, 1, 1, \dots, 1, 2]$ or $[2, 1, 1, \dots, 1, 2]$. If it equals $[1, 1, 1, \dots, 1, 2]$, then $n/a = F_m/F_{m-1}$. If it equals $[2, 1, 1, \dots, 1, 2]$, then $n/a = F_m/F_{m-2}$. □

5.3.1. An Upper Bound on the Number of Vertices of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$

The dominant term in the sum $\sum_{i=0}^m q_i$ is $q_0 = \lfloor n/a \rfloor$ when a is small in comparison to n . Thus, when a is small, a good upper bound for $\text{area}(P_{a,n}^{(1)})$ is $(n - \lfloor n/a \rfloor)$.

The length of the continued fraction of a rational number is simply the number of steps taken by the Euclidean algorithm to find the greatest common divisor of the numerator and denominator of the rational number. Thus, standard results on the computational complexity of the Euclidean algorithm translate to results on the number of vertices of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$. Knuth’s formulation of Lamé’s theorem [7, Chapter 4, Section 5, Subsection 3.0] is of particular interest.

Theorem 7 (Lamé, 1844). *For $N \geq 1$, let u, v be integers, with $u > v > 0$, such that it takes the Euclidean algorithm exactly N division steps to calculate $\text{gcd}(u, v)$. Furthermore, let u be the smallest possible integer satisfying this requirement. Then*

$$u = F_{N+2} \text{ and } v = F_{N+1},$$

where F_k is the k -th Fibonacci number.

An immediate consequence of Equation (2) and Theorem 7 is that

$$\# \text{ vertices of } P_{F_{N+1}, F_{N+2}}^{(1)} = 2N;$$

thereby demonstrating that there is no finite bound for the number of vertices of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$. Another consequence of Theorem 7 is that when we apply the Euclidean algorithm to determine $\gcd(a, n)$, the number of division steps is less than or equal to $(2.078 \log(n) + 0.6723)$. Consequently,

$$\# \text{ vertices of } P_{a,n}^{(1)} \leq 4.156 \log(n) + 3.3446.$$

5.3.2. A Couple of Averages

We now discuss the average value of the number of vertices of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$ and the average value of the area of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$. In both cases n is fixed and a varies. Let $T(m, n)$ denote the number of division steps needed when the inputs to the Euclidean algorithm are m and n , and let

$$\tau_n = \frac{1}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{0 \leq m < n, \gcd(m,n)=1} T(m, n).$$

It has been shown that

$$\tau_n \approx \frac{12 \log(2)}{\pi^2} \log(n) + 1.467$$

(see [7, page 372, Equation 60]). From this it follows that, on average,

$$\# \text{ vertices } \left(P_{a,n}^{(1)} \right) \approx 1.685 \log(n).$$

Furthermore, for a fixed n , the average value of $\text{area} \left(P_{a,n}^{(1)} \right)$ is approximately $(n - (6/\pi^2) \log^2 n)$. We obtain this by applying a result of Viktor Popov.³ Let us explain. For $a, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, with $\gcd(a, n) = 1$, let $S(a, n)$ denote the sum of the partial quotients of the continued fraction expansion of a/n . For p prime, Popov [8] proved that

$$\sum_{1 \leq a < p} S(a, p) = \frac{6}{\pi^2} p \log^2(p) + O(p \log(p)).$$

Furthermore, he stated, without proof, that for large n

$$\sum_{1 \leq a < n} S(a, n) \approx \frac{6}{\pi^2} \varphi(n) \log^2(n).$$

³Viktor Nikolaevich Popov was an eminent theoretical physicist highly regarded for his work on the quantization of non-abelian gauge fields.

If the continued fraction expansion of n/a , with $n > a > 0$, is $[q_0, q_1, \dots, q_m]$, then the continued fraction expansion of a/n is $[0, q_0, q_1, \dots, q_m]$. Consequently, $S(n, a) = S(a, n)$. Equation (4) states that

$$\text{area} \left(P_{a,n}^{(1)} \right) = n - S(a, n).$$

Consequently, we can invoke Popov’s result to conclude that, on average,

$$\text{area} \left(P_{a,n}^{(1)} \right) \approx n - (6/\pi^2) \log^2 n.$$

5.4. Conjectural Relationships with Modular Forms

We now indulge in a short interlude of fanciful speculation! From the analytic number theory point of view, the average number of vertices of $P_{a,n}^{(1)}$, with fixed n , is reciprocal to the density of prime numbers less than n . We wonder if this can be viewed as a bridge that connects the levels of interior hulls of lattice points and the levels of modular forms and the modular form space’s dimensions for each level. The latter information is obtained from the Riemann–Roch theorem. Our speculation is that the level of the interior hull corresponds to the level of the congruence subgroup and that there is an integer quantity associated to $P_{a,n}^{(N)}$ that corresponds to the level N modular form space’s dimension.

Our “reasoning” is as follows. Heuristically speaking, the number of lattice points in the interior of a polygon has the same magnitude as the area of the polygon. In the case of modular forms, the volume is linked to the spectrum of certain invariant operators via trace formulae. For example, consider a family of Hecke operators acting on a vector space of modular forms of a given weight and a given level of congruence subgroup of the modular group. The trace of the identity operator gives the dimension of that space. That is, it gives the dimension of the space of modular forms with given weight and level. This quantity is traditionally calculated via the Riemann–Roch theorem, or trace formulae such as Selberg’s or Arthur’s. In particular, a complete set of dimension formulae have been computed in [12, Proposition 6.1]. To us, these dimension formulae have a similar flavour to Equation (3).

5.5. An Interesting Degenerate Case in \mathbb{R}^3

One of our future goals is to investigate the interior hulls of clean lattice parallelepipeds. However, there is an interesting case in \mathbb{R}^3 to which we know the answer. Let us elaborate. George White [13] proved that all the nonvertex lattice points in a clean parallelepiped that arises from an empty tetrahedron are coplanar. Consequently, the interior hull of this parallelepiped is always a lattice polygon and never a lattice polytope. It follows that our central result applies mutatis mutandis in this special case. We expand on this remark.

Let \mathcal{P} be a clean lattice parallelepiped that has at least one lattice point in its interior. Without loss of generality we can assume that one of the vertices is at the origin and consequently we can write \mathcal{P} as

$$\mathcal{P} = \{t_1\mathbf{v}_1 + t_2\mathbf{v}_2 + t_3\mathbf{v}_3; \mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \mathbf{v}_3 \in \mathbb{Z}^3, 0 \leq t_1, t_2, t_3 \leq 1\}.$$

Since \mathcal{P} is clean, we can find a unimodular map that sends

$$\mathbf{v}_1 \mapsto (1, 0, 0), \mathbf{v}_2 \mapsto (0, 1, 0), \mathbf{v}_3 \mapsto (a, b, c),$$

with $a, b, c \in \mathbb{Z}$, $c = \text{vol}(\mathcal{P})$, $1 \leq a, b < c$, $\gcd(a, c) = \gcd(b, c) = 1$. Thus we can identify \mathcal{P} with the parallelepiped

$$\mathcal{P}_{a,b,c} = \{t_1(1, 0, 0) + t_2(0, 1, 0) + t_3(a, b, c); 0 \leq t_1, t_2, t_3 \leq 1\}.$$

Let $\mathcal{T}_{a,b,c}$ denote the tetrahedron,

$$\{t_1(1, 0, 0) + t_2(0, 1, 0) + t_3(a, b, c); 0 \leq t_1, t_2, t_3 \leq 1, 0 \leq t_1 + t_2 + t_3 \leq 1\}.$$

If $\mathcal{T}_{a,b,c}$ is empty, that is, does not contain any lattice points other than its vertices, then for some $x \in \mathbb{N}$ the interior hulls $\mathcal{P}_{a,b,c}^{(k)}$ can be identified with the interior hulls $P_{x,c}^{(k)}$. The key is to invoke White’s theorem [13]. White showed that if $\mathcal{T}_{a,b,c}$ is empty, then

$$a = 1 \text{ or } b = 1 \text{ or } (1 - a - b) \bmod c = 1.$$

It now follows that if $\mathcal{T}_{a,b,c}$, with $c > 1$, is empty, then $\mathcal{P}_{a,b,c}$ is unimodularly equivalent to $\mathcal{P}_{1,x,c}$ for some $x \in \mathbb{N}$ with $1 \leq x < c$ and $\gcd(x, c) = 1$. All of the interior lattice points in $\mathcal{P}_{1,x,c}$ lie in the parallelogram with vertices $(1, 0, 0)$, $(1, 1, 0)$, $(1, x, c)$, and $(1, x + 1, c)$. Clearly, we can identify this parallelogram with the parallelogram $P_{x,c} \subset \mathbb{R}^2$, and consequently $\mathcal{P}_{a,b,c}^{(k)}$ can be identified with $P_{x,c}^{(k)} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$.

The interested reader can consult both [5, Chapter 15] and [6] for further information on White’s theorem.

Acknowledgements. Our exposition and proofs are based on Stark’s geometric approach to continued fractions in Chapter 7 of his introductory textbook on number theory [11]. The clarity of his exposition (both written and pictorial) played a significant role in guiding us in our work. We should also mention the following anecdote. At the Integers 2009 conference, the second author asked Kevin Ford a question about counting visible points inside $P_{a,n}$ and he casually replied that continued fractions might give insight into the problem. The second author was never able to implement Ford’s remark with regard to visible points, but here it turned out to be most fruitful. *Bahut Shukriya* (many thanks in Urdu) Kevin!

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